

ChEESE

HPC CODE AUDIT EXPLAINER: THE ChEESE CoE EXPERIENCE

Understanding how code audits contribute to an integrated performance optimisation methodology for HPC projects

Prepared By :
ChEESE CoE WP2 and WP7

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Credits

Document prepared by:

Piero Lanucara
Senior technologist
at CINECA

Jose Gracia
Head of Scalable Programming
Models and Tools at HLRS

Aerton Guimarães
Communications and
Dissemination Officer at BSC

Varvara Vedia-García
Communications and
Dissemination Officer at CSIC

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1. Introduction

High-Performance Computing (HPC) is essential for advancing scientific applications that simulate complex **geophysical phenomena** such as earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, and tsunamis. To fully exploit modern supercomputing systems, these applications must continuously improve in terms of performance, scalability, and portability on heterogeneous architectures.

Within the ChEESA-2P project, Work Package 2 (WP2) has developed a structured methodology to support the evolution of flagship simulation codes. This approach combines performance assessment, optimisation, portability, and monitoring to drive **measurable improvements** over time.

The WP2 workflow includes several key steps: code audits, carried out in collaboration with the **POP project**, to establish performance baselines and identify bottlenecks; mini-app extraction and performance portability campaigns; optimisation and code restructuring; and continuous performance monitoring. Together, these elements form a feedback loop that enables sustained code evolution.

In this context, code audits represent the **entry point** of the process, guiding subsequent optimisation efforts within a broader methodology.

This document presents a set of **frequently asked questions** to explain how this workflow operates in practice, focusing on the role of code audits within the overall process.

2. ChEESA Code Audits

WHAT ARE CHEESE CODE AUDITS?

Within the ChEESA WP2 methodology, code audits represent the entry point of a broader performance optimisation workflow. They are **detailed evaluations** of the computer programs (called **flagship codes**) used in the project.

The goal is to **see how efficiently these programs perform** when running large scientific simulations on supercomputers.

WHY ARE THEY IMPORTANT?

They help **identify parts of the code that slow down performance** -called bottlenecks- monitor their evolution, and measure improvement through performance metrics, ensuring better efficiency and scalability on EuroHPC systems.

3. How Are Audits Done?

Each code is tested twice during the project:

- **First audit:** early on, to measure the starting point and find the main issues.
- **Second audit:** two years later, to see how much performance has improved.

Both assessments use the **same scientific example and the same supercomputing system** to make results comparable.

The audit data is analysed by the project **Performance Optimisation and Productivity (POP) using**

their tools and metrics, which are standard methods developed by European HPC experts to evaluate and improve code performance.

Audit scale refers to the number of cores or GPUs that were used for the audit, respectively. This shows clearly that we do our performance audits "at scale" and not for small scale toy setups.

The results of these audits provide the foundation for further optimisation, portability efforts, and performance improvements within the WP2 methodology.

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4. Who Is Involved & Where?

The process is led by **HLRS (High Performance Computing Center Stuttgart)**, with contributions from other ChEESE partners including CSIC, INGV, CINECA, TUM, LMU, UMA, CNRS, IPGP, CSC, UM, and SU.

Code owners are closely involved throughout the process to ensure realistic and meaningful testing conditions.

The audits are performed whenever possible and are carried out on **EuroHPC systems such as Leonardo, LUMI, and MareNostrum 5**, representing some of the most advanced computing architectures in Europe.

5. Key Benefits

The audits focus on three main objectives:

IDENTIFY PERFORMANCE BOTTLENECKS AND GUIDE OPTIMISATION

LOCATE AREAS IN THE CODE THAT HINDER PERFORMANCE.

ESTABLISH BASELINE

SET A STARTING POINT TO MEASURE PROGRESS.

MEASURE PROGRESS

TRACK PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENTS USING METRICS.

The outcome of each audit is a **detailed report including POP performance metrics** and targeted recommendations.

By comparing results from the first and second audits, teams can clearly assess **how each code has improved and where further optimisation is needed**. This helps ensure that the software is ready for large-scale, real-world applications.

By improving performance, ChEESSE enables faster and more detailed simulations of natural hazards such as earthquakes, tsunamis, and volcanic eruptions, directly supporting better **risk assessment and disaster preparedness**.

The code audits not only identify performance issues but also enable a structured path towards continuous optimisation.

6. Portability & Sustainability

The audits are a central component of the broader WP2 methodology, designed to improve performance, portability, and sustainability of simulation codes.

While initially applied to ChEESE-2P flagship codes and mini-apps, **this approach is intended to be generalisable and applicable to other HPC codes.**

By formalising the WP2 workflow as a structured, reusable service, **external research groups and developers can benefit from ChEESE expertise without needing** to replicate the full infrastructure. This includes code audits, mini-app extraction, porting and tuning, performance monitoring, and the development of templates, documentation, and best practices.

Training sessions and workshops further support adoption, helping integrate this methodology into other HPC projects.

Unlike approaches that rely solely on execution time, the POP methodology separates time spent in user code from time spent in parallel runtimes such as MPI or CUDA.

This makes it possible to attribute performance issues to specific causes, such as load imbalance, communication patterns, or bandwidth limitations.

Two key challenges are preparing codes so that performance analysis tools can collect meaningful data, and selecting use cases that are both representative of real production scenarios and efficient in terms of resource usage.

7. Real Impact & Future Collaborations

WP2 has played a key role in **connecting community codes with broader European HPC initiatives**, supporting their progression towards production-level and Grand Challenge applications.

This has enabled contributions to several major projects, including:

- **DT-GEO**, where WP2 codes and expertise supported the development of digital twin workflows for geophysics
- **Geo-INQUIRE**, which leveraged flagship codes and domain expertise to strengthen geoscience research infrastructures
- **EuPEX**, which benefited from WP2 performance engineering in the context of exascale readiness and application co-design

Through these collaborations, WP2 extends the impact of ChEESA beyond the project itself, contributing to a **stronger and more connected European HPC ecosystem**.

Geo-INQUIRE

EUPEX
European Pilot for Exascale

DT-GEO

8. Takeaways / How to Learn More

Code audits go beyond technical verification: they provide the foundation for improving performance, portability, and readiness for **future supercomputing systems**.

Within ChEESE WP2, they act as the starting point of an **integrated process** that combines optimisation, portability, and monitoring.

This approach enables continuous improvement of HPC applications and supports their evolution across changing computing architectures.

Learn More:

For more information about the ChEESE Centre of Excellence (CoE) for Exascale in Solid Earth activities, methodology, and public resources:

 www.cheese2.eu

 ChEESE CoE

 [cheese5311126](https://github.com/cheese5311126)

 [@cheesecoe.bsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/cheesecoe.bsky.social)

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